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- Poetry
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“TOXIC PEERS OR MY TOXIC PRESENCE: A REFLECTIVE ESSAY”

I had a colleague whose actions continually weakened my humanity. Their unstoppable tittle-tattle, and strong refusal to cooperate in the team started to trigger my hell-like thinking. At first their irregular criticism and presence, I took as invisible. The hindrance of a toxic colleagues was a rapid decline in my excitement of reporting at work and a suffering from overthinking for being unjustly dismissed and terrorized.

Their presence frequently diverted me and relive the things I may have said or done differently causing to the suffering of productivity. Their avoidance in participating in group initiatives, choosing to endure the deafening silence rather than run the presence of conflict and chaos. Despite proof of prior achievements, I started to doubt my skills, and my job satisfaction tumbled. Because of this, I started honestly recording incidents— how they affected my work. Having readable notes helped me talk about the problem with confidence, bringing clarity to the emotional vagueness.

A mediated session was started to offer a performance-improvement plan and clarify expectations. Although it wasn't a perfect and longterm solution, the toxicity was recognized and limited. Importantly, I discovered the strength of world survivor. I stopped self blaming, regained my own strength and purpose, and returned my professional self with the presence of Wisdom.

In the end, I learned from this certain situation that toxic conduct does not define my being "Toto Glenn" and does not have to define my self generated output either. By justly raising awareness, honestly keeping diaries, and humbly getting help, I was able to turn a bad circumstance into a jumping-off point for my own growth and development. I now place a high value on respectful and openminded surroundings, understanding each attitude and behavior, and without mental reservation communication—all of which are critical for promoting both individual wellbeing and productive teamwork.

Lastly, before judging of toxic peers, evaluate our toxicity first. May be in the end, our presence is the toxic, not them.

